

Developing a CubeSat to track the global movement of water, carbon and sediment across landscapes

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The NASA/CNES Surface Water and Ocean Topography satellite (SWOT), scheduled for launch in late 2021, will provide unprecedented observations of water surface elevation globally. These observations will be used to track the movement of freshwater across Earth's land surface, a key component in the water cycle. However, SWOT will not be able to track changes in surface water quality (e.g. suspended sediment, dissolved carbon, algal blooms). Further, SWOT's radar instrument will provide returns that contain complex backscattering effects that are expected to complicate scientific interpretations. Optical sensors, like those that can be mounted on small CubeSats, can be used to overcome both of these limitations.

Here we propose the launch of a relatively inexpensive CubeSat, containing an optical sensor that will provide complementary water quality and classification information to SWOT. The proposed CubeSat, tentatively named "SWOTlet", would orbit closely with the SWOT satellite and provide simultaneous optical observations of Earth's surface (Figure 1). SWOTlet's optical sensor would ideally have similar characteristics as the HICO instrument aboard the International Space Station: an imaging spectrometer sensitive to wavelengths between 0.4 and 0.7 micrometers. This range is optimized for water quality characterization like suspended sediment concentration, colored dissolved organic material, or harmful cyanobacterial and algal blooms. Additionally, we propose that SWOTlet's optical sensor contain a band in the infrared range (e.g. SWIR at 1.55-1.75 micrometers) to be used to classify water, snow, ice, and cloud coverage. Note that a very simple, off-the-shelf RGB+NIR optical sensor like those used by Planet DoveSats could also provide highly useful data at a lower cost than an imaging spectrometer.

The proposed CubeSat would greatly expand the scientific utility of the SWOT mission by providing cotemporal observations of water quality, wetland vegetation cover, and other phenomenological characteristics of Earth's surface. In rivers, paired observations of water discharge from SWOT and observations of water quality from SWOTlet could be used to track the flux of biogeochemical constituents like silica, carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus across continents. Changes in vegetation cover throughout the growing season, which would be tracked by SWOTlet, could be associated with changes in hydrological conditions observed by SWOT. Such variations are of particular

Figure 1: The proposed SWOTlet satellite would provide cotemporal optical observations to complement SWOT radar returns.

concern in the Arctic where thawing permafrost is drastically impacting ecosystems and landscapes. In lakes, colored dissolved organic material could be monitored with SWOTlet, along with changes in water levels from SWOT, to infer variations in greenhouse gas emissions from these water bodies. Along the coast, simultaneous optical observations of sediment plumes, combined with water surface topography and hydrodynamic models, could be used to infer oceanic transport of water, organic carbon, and sediment in these environments. Taken together, the launch of SWOTlet would expand the SWOT mission from one devoted to the study of Earth's water cycle to a mission for the study of the carbon cycle, sediment cycle, and nitrogen cycle.

A single CubeSat could provide high-resolution imagery (e.g. 10 m) capable of resolving fine variations within water bodies and their bordering vegetation across SWOT's 120-km radar swath (Figure 1). This optical imagery would be useful for enhancing the interpretation of SWOT's radar returns by flagging problematic radar effects like layover, specular reflection, and other geometric distortions inherent to imaging radar systems. An optical imager could also be used to identify surface features like ice and inundated vegetation, which often appear highly distorted in radar imagery. One acknowledged limitation of the proposed optical sensor is that it will not be able to provide surface observations at night or during cloudy conditions, unlike the SWOT radar instrument. However, we believe that the relative benefits of including an optical CubeSat for SWOT far outweigh this limitation: SWOT is a US\$1 billion satellite mission focused on the movement of water. For a relatively small investment, the launch of SWOTlet would transform the SWOT mission by broadening its scientific focus to the global movement of carbon, nitrogen, and sediment, in addition to water.

Texas A&M University is an ideal primary sponsor of the SWOTlet satellite. TAMU has a top-ranked Aerospace Engineering program with considerable experience in designing and launching CubeSats. Additionally, TAMU has recently began a Strategic University Research Partnership with the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, which is where the SWOT mission originated and where the U.S. portion of the satellite is being designed and built. This novel project would provide many research opportunities for TAMU faculty, research staff, and students, as well as initiating new research collaborations. It would also strengthen the university's space-grant mission and our existing partnership with NASA. Unlike government civilian satellites, which are legally limited to a spatial resolution of 10 m or greater, a university-funded CubeSat could be designed with a sensor with a finer resolution. Further, a university-sponsored CubeSat system would make it possible to provide the remote sensing products described above to all researchers in need of optical data to complement the SWOT measurements.

Overall, the collection of cotemporal optical observations by SWOTlet with radar observations from SWOT represents a considerable mission utility multiplier for the SWOT program with significant and wide-ranging benefits across scientific disciplines. It is a tractable and useful investment. In fact, adding an optical sensor to SWOT is such an attractive concept that it was proposed as the next generation of the SWOT satellite by many of the core members of the SWOT Science Team during the most recent National Research Council Decadal Survey ([Pavelsky et al., 2016](#)). Rather than waiting for the next SWOT-like satellite system to be developed, we have the opportunity to actuate this concept now, using a CubeSat. This experiment may also aid in the development of the next SWOT-like satellite mission, of which TAMU would be well-positioned for involvement.